

Relation between Lattice Energy and Melting Points of Some Crystalline Substances. Part VII. Lattice Energy in Relation to Physical Properties of Some Metals

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From investigation of some possible relationships between the lattice energy, $-U_o$, of some metals and their physical properties, the newly calculated lattice energy, $-U_o$, of a transition metal, as obtained from the equation $-U_o = I \times v + S$ has been found to be in better conformity with the physical properties like temperature coefficient of thermal expansion (α), compressibility (β), etc. than that obtained from the conventional procedures³.

In an earlier communication¹, the lattice energy*, $-U_o$, for a transition metal was calculated from the equation:

$$-U_o = I \times v + S \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where ' I ' is the first ionisation potential, ' v ', the metallic valency as given by Pauling², instead of the chemical valency, and ' S ', the latent heat of sublimation of the metal concerned. The number of electrons in the valency shell of a metal atom has been used by earlier workers, instead of ' v ', for calculating the lattice energies of metals like Cu, Ag, Au, Zn, Cd, and Hg, besides alkali and alkaline earths³. It was pointed out¹ that the values of $-U_o$, thus obtained, were too low in the case of transition metals, as had already been remarked by Ketelaar³. On the other hand, it was pointed out that $-U_o$, obtained from equation (1), appeared to be in conformity with the high melting points of transition metals. Further, an approximate proportionality appears to exist between $-U_o$ and the corresponding absolute melting point, T_m , in similar transition metals.

It has been remarked above that the values of $-U_o$ for transition metals, obtained from conventional procedures³, are too low, but those obtained from equation (1) appear

1. Gopal and Hussain, *this Journal*, 1962, **39**, 827.

* U_o is the binding energy of the metal. The use of the term "lattice energy" is justified on the ground that the number of electrons involved in the binding, per atom, is given by ' v ', Pauling's metallic valency in the case of transition metals. One has to imagine that the metal is formed out of v -fold ionised atoms, in the hybridised state, and electrons just as in alkali and alkaline earth metals, the formation of the metal is imagined from the n -fold ionised atoms and electrons, ' n ' being the chemical valency of the atom and these ' n ' electrons per atom are involved in the binding of these metals. The energy given out in the formation of a metal, per g. atom, is given by

$$-U_o = I \times v + S \quad (\text{in transition metals}) \text{ and}$$

$$-U_o = I \times n + S \quad (\text{in alkali and alkaline earth metals})$$

Since $-U_o$ has been called 'lattice energy' in the latter cases, it should also be called lattice energy in the former on the same ground (cf. Ketelaar³, p 322).

2. Pauling, "Nature of Chemical Bond", Cornell University Press, Ithaca, New York, 1960, pp. 394-403.

3. Ketelaar, "Chemical Constitution", Elsevier Publishing Co., London, 1958, p. 322.

to correspond to their high melting points. In order to justify more fully the $-U_0$ values, obtained from equation (1), some additional evidence must be presented. In view of impossibility of direct experimental determination of $-U_0$, the best way to show that equation (1) does give $-U_0$ of the correct magnitude is to show that these values of $-U_0$ are in better conformity with the physical properties of the metals concerned than those obtained from the conventional methods, using chemical valency electrons ' ν ' in place of ' π ' in equation (1) or those obtained from Wilson's equation³. In what follows, an attempt has been made to examine the relationships between $-U_0$ and some physical properties, related to $-U_0$, in various metals. The physical properties, which are experimentally known and could be expected to be related to $-U_0$ of a metal, are the absolute melting point, T_m , the coefficient of thermal expansion, α , latent heats of fusion, L_f , and of sublimation L_s (or S), and compressibility, β , etc.⁴⁻⁷. In order to make use of these properties to decide which value of $-U_0$ is more acceptable, it is necessary to establish relationship between the various experimentally determined properties, mentioned above, and $-U_0$, so as to show that similar behaviour is exhibited when their $-U_0$'s are matched with these physical properties of the metal in question. We have chosen the absolute melting point, T_m , and have matched it with the different physical properties of respective metals in order to set up a general pattern of behaviour to be expected in different cases. T_m is then replaced by $-U_0$, both the conventional and that from equation (1), to see which value of $-U_0$ offers a better and reasonable correspondence.

Relation among L_f , L_s , T_m , and $-U_0$

It is already well known that the entropies of fusion of most metals are around 2 cal./g. atom/degree⁸, extreme values being 1.7 cal. and 2.3 cal. Similar² relationship exists between L_s and T_m , the ratio L_s/T_m being in most cases is around 50 cal./g. atom/degree, although for alkali metals it is nearer to 60 cal. Those relationships are well known but have been reproduced here in Table I to impress our line of arguments. When $-U_0$ from equation (1) is substituted for the corresponding T_m , the same general behaviour is observed (Table I).

It may be seen that L_f/U_0 values are about 4.5×10^{-3} and L_s/U_0 , about 8.10×10^{-2} with slightly higher values for the alkali metals. If the conventional values of $-U_0$, referred to earlier³, are used, these ratios for alkali and alkaline earth metals remain unchanged (because $-U_0$ is unchanged). For Cu, Ag, Au, and other transition metals, their respective values become 11×10^{-3} and 30×10^{-2} . These values are very high. The conventional $-U_0$ values appear therefore to be rather low.

Relation among the Coefficient of Thermal Expansion α , T_m , and $-U_0$

From general considerations it appears that the higher the melting point T_m , the tighter the binding and the smaller the temperature coefficient of thermal expansion α . In other words, α should vary inversely as the melting point, T_m , i.e. αT_m should be constant. This

4. Partington, "Advanced Treatise on Physical Chemistry", Vol. III, 1952, p. 349.

5. Meyerling and Druyvesteyn, *Physica*, 1949, 8, 851.

6. Druyvesteyn, *ibid.*, p. 862.

7. Gopal, this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 55.

8. Taylor and Glasstone, "Treatise on Physical Chemistry", Vol. II, D. Van Nostrand Co., Inc., New York, 1952, p. 370.

has already been observed by some workers^{9,10}. The inverse proportionality between α and T_m is obvious from Table II and the product αT_m is very nearly constant for most metals.

TABLE I

Relations among L_f , L_n , T_m , and $-U_0$ of some metals.

Metal.	L_f (kcal.)	L_n (or β) (kcal.)	T_m (°K)	$-U_0$ (kcal.)	L_f/T_m	L_f/U_0	L_n/T_m	L_n/U_0
Li	1.10	37.1	453	161	2.4×10^{-3}	6.8×10^{-3}	8.2×10^{-2}	23.0×10^{-2}
Na	0.63	26	371	145	1.7	4.4	7.0	18.0
K	0.57	22	336	122	1.7	4.7	6.4	18.0
Rb	0.52	21	312	117	1.7	4.5	6.6	18.0
Cs	0.50	19	302	109	1.7	4.6	6.2	17.0
Mg	2.20	36	923	558	2.3	3.9	3.9	6.5
Ca	2.20	42	1123	467	2.6	4.7	3.7	9.0
Sr	2.20	39	1043	424	2.1	5.2	3.7	9.2
Ba	2.00	42	977	392	2.1	5.1	4.3	11.0
Cu	3.10	82	1356	1006	2.3	2.9	6.1	7.7
				260*		*12.0		*31.0
Ag	2.70	60	1234	1034	2.2	2.6	5.6	6.6
				244		*11.0		*28
Au	3.00	91	1336	1271	2.3	2.4	6.9	7.5
				304*		*10.0		30.0
Fe	3.90	94	1808	1176	2.1	3.3	5.2	7.9
Co	3.70	85	1765	1164	2.1	3.2	4.8	7.4
Ni	4.20	85	1726	1135	2.4	3.7	4.9	7.8
Os	6.70	125	2973	1369	2.2	4.7	4.2	9.1
Ir	6.00	120	2716	1364	2.4	4.8	4.4	9.0
Pt	5.20	127	2042	1371	2.6	3.8	6.2	9.0
Ru	6.10	120	2723	1184	2.2	5.2	4.3	10.1
Rh	5.20	115	2233	1179	2.3	4.4	5.2	9.9
Pd	4.10	110	1825	1284	2.3	3.2	6.0	8.6
Cr	7.50	88	2186	1020	1.6	3.4	4.0	8.6
Mo	6.70	160	2883	1176(?)	3.3	5.7	5.6	13.6
W	8.40	210	3653	1316(?)	2.3	6.4	5.8	16.0

*Conventional values of $-U_0$ and the corresponding ratios.

For alkali and alkaline earth metals, αT_m is about 0.028 and for the rest, about 0.02. When $-U_0$ from equation (1) is substituted for T_m , one finds a similar behaviour, namely $-U_0/\alpha$ values being about 0.01 to 0.02 in most cases with exception of Cr, Mo, and W. With the conventional values of $-U_0$ for Cu, Ag, and Au, $-U_0/\alpha$ is about 0.0043 which is obviously very low. Here again, the conventional values of $-U_0$ do not appear to fit in with the related physical properties.

Relation among Compressibility β , T_m , and $-U_0$

A convenient function to test the relation between $-U_0$ and the compressibility, β , directly, without first referring to T_m , has been advanced by Biswas¹¹ according

9. Ratnowsky, *Ann. Phys.*, 1912, **38**, 837.

10. Wiebe, *ibid.*, 1905, **19**, 1076. See ref. No 4, p. 365.

11. *This Journal*, 1928, **5**, 561.

to whom $U_0 \beta^{1/4}$ is a constant for metals. This function for a number of metals has been calculated and is shown in Table III.

TABLE II

Relation among the coefficient of thermal expansion α , T_m , and $-U_0$.

Metal.	$\alpha \times 10^6$.	αT_m .	$\alpha (-U_0)$.	Metal.	$\alpha \times 10^6$.	αT_m .	$\alpha (-U_0)$.
Li	56	0.025	0.010	Fe	11.7	0.021	0.014
Na	71	0.026	0.010	Co	12.3	0.022	0.014
K	83	0.028	0.010	Ni	12.8	0.022	0.015
Rb	80	0.028	0.010	Os	6.1	0.018	0.008
Cs	97	0.029	0.010	Ir	6.5	0.018	0.009
Ca	25	0.028	0.012	Pt	8.9	0.018	0.012
Sr	23	0.024	0.010	Ru	9.1	0.024	0.011
Ba	27	0.027	0.010	Rh	8.4	0.019	0.010
Mg	27	0.025	0.015	Pd	11.8	0.022	0.015
Cu	17	0.023	0.017	Cr	8.2	0.018	0.008
			(0.0043)*				
Ag	19	0.023	0.019	Mo	4.0	0.012	0.004**
			(0.0040)*				
Au	14	0.019	0.017	W	4.0	0.015	0.006**
			(0.0043)*				

*Values obtained from the conventional values of $-U_0$.

**Attention has already been drawn to rather unsatisfactory nature of $-U_0$ values obtained from eq. (1) in these and some other cases.¹¹

TABLE III

Relation among $-U_0$, compressibility, and T_m .

Metal.	$-\beta \times 10^7$.	$-\beta^{1/4} T_m \times 10^7$.	$\beta^{1/4} U_0 \times 10^7$.	Metal.	$-\beta \times 10^7$.	$-\beta^{1/4} T_m \times 10^7$.	$\beta^{1/4} U_0 \times 10^7$
Li	87	1384	493	Fe	5.9	2818	1832
Na	156	1311	511	Co	5.4	2690	1774
K	357	1461	529	Ni	6.3	2619	1723
Rb	520	1490	557	Os	..	..	..
Ca	700	1553	558	Ir	2.7	3481	1749
Cs	57	3086	1283	Pt	3.6	2813	1888
Sr	82	3138	1276	Ru	3.4	3698	1608
				Rh	3.6	3085	1823
Ba	102	3106	1240	Pd	5.3	2773	1948
Mg	30.0	2157	1304				
Cu	7.2	2221	1746	Cr	6.1	3400	1603
			(426)*				
Ag	9.9	2189	1834	Mo	3.6	3986	1620
			(433)*				
Au	5.8	2075	1970	W	3.2	4873	1760
			(472)*				

*From the conventional values of $-U_0$.

From Table III it is evident that $U_0 \beta^{1/4}$ values form a constant set for alkali metals (≈ 525), another set for alkaline earth metals (≈ 1200), and a third constant set for the rest (≈ 1700). With the conventional values of $-U_0$, $U_0 \beta^{1/4}$ for Cu, Ag, and Au is only about 450 which is even smaller than that for alkali metals. The very clear division of various

metals into three categories with regard to their $U_0\beta^{1/4}$ values appears to be accidental since the corrected values of $-U_0$ in some cases, like Cr, Mo, and W, will considerably increase the values of $U_0\beta^{1/4}$ in these cases. The values of $-T_m\beta^{1/4}$, recorded in Table III, cannot be clearly put into three categories. One can put them into one for alkali metals (≈ 1500) and another for the rest with wide haphazard variations ($\approx 2000-4900$). All the same, the important and significant fact is that $U_0\beta^{1/4}$ for transition metals, obtained with conventional $-U_0$, are very low indeed. This certainly shows that these $-U_0$ values do not correspond to the compressibility of these metals.

From the evidence adduced above, it appears that the conventional values of $-U_0$ of metals, excluding alkali and alkaline earth, do not correspond to their physical properties. On the other hand, U_0 's obtained from equation (1), although only of rough accuracy and needing a theoretical justification, are in a reasonable agreement and in a better correspondence with the physical properties like T_m , α , and β , etc.

The aim of the present and the previous communication (Part VI) of this series is not to offer the final solution but only to draw the attention of the theoretical chemists and physicists to this rather neglected but important problem and to provoke them to accept its challenge and work out its final solution.

Thanks of the authors are due to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for financial assistance and to the Head of the Chemistry Department and authorities of the Lucknow University for the facilities provided during the course of this investigation.

CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW, U. P.

Received February 3, 1963.